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**What is the Potential of ICTs to
Improve Education in
Low and Middle Income Countries?**

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Abstract

*Worldwide, actors hold high hopes about the use of technologies in education. Evaluating literature on different aspects related to the use of technologies in education, this paper aims at bringing together the dispersed knowledge in this field. It addresses the question: **What is the potential of information and communication technologies (ICTs) to improve education in low and middle income countries (LMICs)?** Based on findings from past and current ICT projects in education in LMICs, this paper determines five factors that seem to be decisive for the success of such initiatives: People, technology, pedagogy, financial cost, and organization. Focusing on primary and secondary education, the author argues that considering the elaborated aspects, ICTs can contribute to advance towards the internationally declared education targets by improving access to education, inclusion, and gender equality as well as quality. Furthermore, experiences on different ICT-initiatives indicate that in some LMIC-contexts, traditional technologies are more promising than recent ones.*

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List of abbreviations

Chinese Renminbi Yuan	CNY
Distance Education Project for Rural Schools	DEPRS
Educational Media Agency	EMA
Information and communication technology	ICT
Information technology	IT
Interactive Radio Instruction program	IRI program
Least developed countries	LDCs
Low and middle income country	LMIC
Massachusetts Institute of Technology	MIT
Millennium Development Goals	MDGs
Ministry of Education, Science and Technology	MoEST
Non-governmental organization	NGO
One Laptop per Child	OLPC
One Tablet per Child	OTPC
Papua New Guinea Sustainable Development Program	PNGSDP
Primary Math and Reading Initiative	PRIMR
Program Alphabétisation de Base par Cellulaire	Program ABC
Project Organizing Committee	PMU
Severe Respiratory Syndrome	SARS
Sustainable Development Goals	SDGs
Teachers' Advisory Centre	TAC
US-Dollar	USD
Voluntary Service Overseas	VSO

1. Introduction

“If your plan is for one year, plant rice. If your plan is for ten years, plant trees. If your plan is for one hundred years, educate children”

(Confucius, 7th Century BC, cited from World Bank Group, 2018, p. 3).

“[E]ducation [...] has many benefits for economies, and for societies as a whole. For individuals, education promotes employment, earnings, and health. It raises pride and opens new horizons. For societies, it drives long-term economic growth, reduces poverty, spurs innovation, strengthens institutions, and fosters social cohesion”

(World Bank Group, 2018, p. 1)

Education has for a long time been seen as key to socioeconomic well-being. For the development of countries that are lagging behind, education is a crucial target. For many years, actors have invested in technology involving initiatives to improve education (Barrera-Osorio and Leigh, 2009, p. 2-23; Easterly, 2001, pp. 71-76; Hanushek & Wößmann, 2012, p. 268; Pritchett, 2001, p. 368; Tamim, Bernard, Borokhovski, Abrami, & Schmid, 2011, pp. 4-5). Perceiving an enormous potential in its capability to solve educational challenges faced by LMICs, the World Education Forum has declared that “Information and communication technologies (ICTs) must be harnessed to strengthen education systems, knowledge dissemination, information access, quality and effective learning, and more effective service provision” (World Education Forum, 2015, p. 8).

Are these hopes and the current hype around ICTs justified? Money does not seem to be the key bottleneck: Worldwide, many governments and organizations are conducting costly ICT projects in education. But critics argue that those are based on assumptions instead of evidence, resulting in frequent failures. While many analyses exist about ICTs in the context of education, they are mostly focused on single aspects such as devices, specific education initiatives or ICT infrastructure.

The author hopes to contribute to providing a sounder basis for the design of such projects. With this goal in mind, this paper aims at providing a comprehensive overview of existing evidence on the use and success of ICTs in the education sector. It addresses

the key question: *What is the potential of ICTs to improve education in LMICs, driven by which success factors?* In order to answer this question, the general relevance of education will be evaluated, followed by a description of the current global situation of education and the internationally declared goals regarding its improvement. Subsequently, a review of the use of ICTs for education purposes with a focus on basic and secondary education in LMICs is presented. In the following analysis, “education” will be considered in a broad definition, including formal and non-formal education, in as well as out of school. Also, although emphasizing recent trends, less modern technologies are included to provide a more complete view of the field. Finally, key success factors are identified and a guideline for the implementation of ICTs in the education sector established.

2. Relevance of Education

One important result of education is the level of economic well-being. Theoretical growth literature points out three main mechanisms how education impacts economic growth (Hanushek & Wößmann, 2010). First, education can grow human capital which in turn raises labor productivity and hence level of output. Second, education can improve the economy’s innovative capacity which fosters growth. Last, the ability to understand and process new information and implement new technologies is improved by education, and consecutively benefits economic growth.

In the macroeconomic literature, the standard method for measuring the economic impact of education on growth is to assess cross-country growth regressions which examine the relationship between the average annual growth of the gross domestic product (GDP) per capita and education, expressed in quantity (commonly as average years) of schooling across the working-age population. The concept of micro-economic studies determines the profitability of educational investments by comparing its benefits and costs. The costs of providing or receiving education are compared to the resulting benefits such as lower rate of unemployment or higher earnings (Hanushek & Wößmann, 2010, p. 245; Sianesi & Van Reenen, 2003, pp. 160-167).

2.1. General findings: Quantity versus quality of schooling

A vast body of empirical evidence on macroeconomic effects affirms the theoretical assumptions that longer schooling increases output per capita (Barro & Lee, 2010, pp. 1-18; Sianesi & Van Reenen, 2003, pp. 157-159). Microeconomic evidence likewise confirms that the rate-of-return on human capital (measured as wage) rises with the level of education (Barro & Lee, 2010, pp. 14-18). Because of the established economic assumption that expanding education increases wages and fosters economic growth, many countries have especially between 1960 and 1990, pursued a development strategy of increasing school enrollment (Easterly, 2001, pp. 71-76; Pritchett, 2001, p. 368).

However, some authors doubt the simple relationship between years of schooling and per capita GDP (Delgado, Henderson and Parmeter, 2012, pp. 1-15; Grimm, 2004, pp. 1-19; Hanushek & Wößmann, 2010, pp. 245-248). Rather, studies indicate that economic growth rates are more strongly correlated with quality of education. Using years of schooling as proxy for the stock of human capital appears to be erroneous. Taking average years of schooling as a measure for education implies that one year of schooling increases knowledge by the same amount regardless of the education system. Differences in quality of education across countries are thus neglected. However, considering average student performance in standardized international tests as a proxy for the quality of education reveals large variations in quality of education across countries (Delgado et al., 2012, pp. 1-16; Hanushek & Wößmann, 2010, pp. 245-248; Hanushek & Wößmann, 2012, pp. 268-269; World Bank Group, 2018, p. 46). The following regressions (figures 1 and 2) on worldwide countries illustrate the correlations between quality respectively quantity of schooling and growth in GDP per capita, considering annual average growth in GDP per capita from 1970-2015, test scores, completed years of schooling and initial GDP per capita. It becomes apparent that quality of schooling (test scores) has a distinctly stronger impact on GDP than quantity (years of schooling).

Figure 1: Test scores & growth

Figure 2: Years of schooling & growth

(Source: World Bank Group, 2018, p. 46)

2.2. Findings for less developed countries

Most studies include worldwide countries, with all levels of development, in such analyses. However, empirical evidence focusing on poor countries reports different findings. For this group of countries, the widespread expansion of education especially from 1960 to 1990 has not consistently translated into economic growth (Easterly, 2001, pp. 71-76; Pritchett, 2001, pp. 381-382). Researchers report several requirements and barriers to an economic impact of education. In developing countries, a lack of functioning institutions and legal systems hinders the provision of quality education and constrains the use of skills in the economy. An increase in education cannot generate economic growth if the economy with a low share of workers in the formal sector does not demand skilled labor. Moreover, educational enrollment needs to meet a minimum level of quality and surpass primary level in order to translate to increased income (Easterly, 2001, pp. 71-84; Grimm, 2004, pp. 1-19). Correspondingly, Barro and Lee (2010) find that the rate of return of education increases with the level of economic development (pp. 14-18).

In spite of empirical evidence of low correlation between economic growth and education in developing countries, many authors stress the benefits of education beyond in-

creasing economic output. For example, it has been empirically shown that female education in low income countries induces more autonomy, eventually increases women's participation in the labor market, and decreases the number of children while improving their survival rate, health and education (Jejeebhoy, 1995, pp. 7-127; Schultz, 1997, pp. 361-376). Furthermore, micro level studies find evidence of positive externalities such as reduced crime, lower welfare dependence, improved public health and parenting (Easterly, 2001, pp. 8-10; Sianesi & Van Reenen, 2003, pp. 160-167). The World Bank (2018) adds that education "generates trust, boosts social capital, and creates institutions that promote inclusion and shared prosperity" (p. 38). The mentioned factors have in turn a positive influence on economic productivity (Sianesi & Van Reenen, 2003, pp. 160-167). Pritchett (2001) suggests that the key lever for improving the payoffs from schooling will be in policy reforms (p. 388).

3. The current global situation of education

3.1. *Persisting deficiencies*

The first barrier to learning is access to schooling. In spite of the expansion in school enrollments, in 2016 61 million children in primary school age (6-11 years) did not attend school, constituting 10% of all children in low- and lower-middle income countries. Additionally, 202 million children of secondary school age (12-17 years) were out of school. Conflicts, violence, and epidemics increasingly pose a barrier to access to schooling (UNESCO, 2016, p. 2; World Bank Group, 2018, p. 8). One third of worldwide out-of-school children live in conflict regions which can even reverse prior progress in education. For example in the Syrian Arab Republic, universal primary enrollment had been achieved by 2000. But due to the arising civil war, by 2016 one fourth of all schools had stopped teaching (UNESCO, 2017a, p. 227; World Bank Group, 2018, p. 60).

In 2014, incidents of the Ebola outbreak and school attacks by Boko Haram in Nigeria lead to school closures ("Nigerian state", 2014; Uzor, 2014). The case of the Severe Respiratory Syndrome (SARS) in 2003 demonstrates that such scenarios are also relevant for highly developed regions. The spread of the virus forced Hong Kong to close all schools. In spite of its elaborated ICT-infrastructure, the education system had not been prepared for such a case, forcing schools and teachers to experiment how to continue education (Fox, 2004).

Unequal school access within countries also needs to be considered. In general, the poor, rural, disabled, ethnic minorities, and female are more likely to be out of school (ECOSOC, 2016, pp. 7-8; World Bank Group, 2018, p. 4-6). Cultural reasons can force girls to leave school before puberty (Haddad & Jurich, 2002, p. 30). Especially in secondary education, attendance can be challenged by the requirement to work or by the distance to a secondary school (Nekatibeb & Tilson, 2004, pp. 123-124; Rodriguez, 2011, p. 4). Furthermore, insufficient teacher availability and skills lead to poor student attendance and high drop-out rates (Thapa & Sein, 2018, p. 2). According to the UNESCO Institute of Statistics, 3.3 million teachers are missing to achieve universal primary education by 2030 (Motivans, 2013).

Low teacher qualification has a negative impact on learning. Shortcomings in education delivery and technical as well as political system problems preserve low quality education (World Bank Group, 2018, p. 4). Decisive factors are unskilled and unmotivated teachers (resulting in teacher absenteeism), insufficient teaching material, and bad school management. School management fails to support teachers and ensure an effective use of resources (Thapa & Sein, 2018, p. 2; World Bank Group, 2018, pp. 9-11).

Weaknesses in governance prevent an efficient alignment of stakeholder interests. For example, private suppliers of education services and bureaucrats may conspire for financial gains which leads to ineffective education policies and low quality education inputs. Often, multiple system elements fail to be aligned; for example, new curricula cannot improve learning without corresponding training of teachers (World Bank Group, 2018, pp. 12-13). Moreover, a lack of reliable, timely data on student assessments makes the detection of deficiencies difficult.

As a consequence, inequalities in acquired skills remain large (ECOSOC, 2016, pp. 7-8; World Bank Group, 2018, p. 5). Even after several years of schooling, many children lack basic literacy and numeracy skills. For Ghana and Malawi for example, assessments showed that over 80% of grade two students were not able to read a single word, and in Nicaragua, only 50% of grade three students could solve $5+6$. This observation leads the World Bank Group (2018) to characterize education in less developed countries as “schooling without learning” (p. 3-5).

3.2. The SDG 4

In 2015, the era of the previous Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) ended. The United Nations General Assembly has defined 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) to enforce unmet targets and add new goals. They were developed to “secure a sustainable, peaceful, prosperous and equitable life on earth for everyone now and in the future” and cover environmental goals, economic and social challenges, and political change, and are intended to be achieved by 2030 (UNESCO, 2017b, p. 6). SDG 4 is dedicated to education. While a remarkable progress has been achieved in school enrolment globally, the target of universal primary education by 2015 as set in the previous MDGs had been missed. Therefore, SDG 4 now puts additional emphasis on educational quality and equity (ECOSOC, 2016, pp. 7-8).

According to UNESCO (2017a), an annual financing gap of 39 billion US-Dollar (USD) in education needs to be overcome to achieve the main SDG 4 targets by 2030. If the goals are to be achieved, international aid to education needs to grow by a factor of six compared to 2012 levels. Lamentably, global aid to education is stagnating since 2009 and its share of total aid is decreasing. The international community is an important stakeholder in this context and should reprioritize educational aid (pp. 271-276).

In the *Incheon Declaration*, the participants of the World Education Forum 2015 present an action framework on how to implement the ambitions set in the SDG 4. The issues that the participants committed to tackle in the learning crisis can be summarized as: Access to primary and secondary school, inclusion and gender equality, quality education, lifelong learning opportunities, and responsibility to crises. Regarding access, it was agreed to ensure public, free, compulsory primary and secondary school for every child – including opportunities for out-of-school children and adolescents. In respect to inclusion and equality, the importance of removing marginalization and disparities that impact access, participation and learning outcomes of disadvantaged groups has been stressed. This effort puts a focus on supporting gender-related issues. To enhance quality of education, education inputs, processes and assessments to measure progress in learning outcomes are to be enhanced. Noticing the role of teachers, the importance of their qualification and motivation is stressed. As lifelong learning mainly affects higher education levels, this aspect will not be included in this overview. Responsibility to crises

is related to access to schooling (World Education Forum, 2015, pp. 7-9). For the remainder of this paper, the relevant SDG 4 are summarized as **access** to education, **inclusion and gender equality**, and **quality of education**.

4. Applications of ICT in the context of education

4.1. Definition "ICT"

Information and communication technology (ICT) is an umbrella term that includes a variety of technologies (Pramanik, Sarkar, & Kandar, 2017, p. 117). "Generally, it consists of the hardware, software, networks and media for the collection, storage, processing, transmission and presentation of information (voice, data, text, and images) as well as the related services" (STOA, 2015, p. 20). In the realm of education, ICTs can be adopted, applied or integrated in order to support, enhance or enable opportunities and practices of education (Dahya, 2016, pp. 9-10). Commonly involved technologies include radio, television, CDs or telephones and modern ICTs based on personal computers, laptops, internet, and mobile phones, with traditional and modern ICTs increasingly uniting due to the digitalization (Haddad, 2007, p. 3; STOA, 2015, p. 20).

4.2. How ICTs can contribute to education

ICTs bring various advantages to education. A variety of technologies exists, each with different properties. ICTs can be applied for education in distance as well as on location, supporting or replacing teachers, and help in the formulation of education policies. They can contribute to education by improving **access** to education, increasing its **quality**, and enhancing its **efficiency**.

Access to education can be improved by technologies that allow teacher and student to be separate physically (out of versus in classroom) and/or in time (teacher and student act at the same or different times). This advantage is especially relevant for the working population that cannot attend classes at pre-determined times (Haddad, 2007, pp. 6-9). Connectivity constitutes an advantage that can facilitate access to practically unlimited amounts of knowledge as well as communication among geographically dispersed learners and instructors. Technology enabled communication can be one- or two-way and its

number of participants vary (Apikul, 2014, p. 8; Pramanik, Sarkar, & Kandar, 2017, pp. 117-118; Tinio, 2003, p. 6).

Financial or socioeconomic constraints, limited teacher availability and social services being disrupted by conflicts, epidemics or natural hazards can exclude people from formal school systems (Fox, 2004; Haddad & Jurich, 2002, p. 29; Uzor, 2014). In such cases, ICT-enabled distance learning offers an alternative channel of education. As Moore et al. (2011) conclude their literature review on definitions in the realm of e-, online-, web-based- and distance learning, there is no clear line between these terms. Distance learning is frequently used as a synonym for the aforementioned terms and seen as the basic version of newer forms (Moore, Dickson-Deane, & Galyen, 2011, pp. 129-130). Therefore, this paper will use the term *distance learning* to refer to education in which during all or most of the teaching the instructor is geographically separated from the learner, and in which all or most of the communication between instructors and learners is conducted through electronic or print mediums (Apikul, 2014, pp. 8-15, Fox, 2014; Prasetyo & Belawati, 2014, pp. 31-33). Depending on the learning objectives, technologies can be combined. Distance learning is usually supported by printed material, audiotapes, CDs, and occasional tutorials (dela Pena-Bandalaria, 2007, p. 7).

Integrated in classroom settings, ICTs can improve instruction and learning **quality**. Technology-based activities enable students to practice skills at their own pace. Audio, video, television, and multi-media software involve multisensorial aspects and enrich learning contents. Abstract concepts can moreover be explained more easily in clips or simulations. Furthermore, access to the internet increases the amount of available information and facilitates interaction among peers. Using ICTs in education can therefore increase student motivation and enable more integrative, interactive, and student-centered approaches (Haddad, 2007, pp. 3-9; Tinio 2003, pp. 7-11).

In addition, the use of technologies can increase **efficiency**. Depending on its features, ICTs can be used to create, store, diffuse, exchange, and consume information. In contrast to information that is bound to a physical medium (such as schoolbooks), digitally shared information does not decrease when shared; the potential to reach a large clientele with a single tool can reduce per-person costs (Barrantes, 2007, p. 4). The resulting scalability is especially relevant for distance learning programs, although it is difficult to

realize if targeted at linguistic minorities or specific contexts (Tedre, Hansson, Mozelius, & Lind, 2011, pp. 1-9; Wagner, 2018, p. 67).

For the development of good education policies, reliable data on student assessments, related infrastructure (educational, physical, and human), finance etc. is required which ICTs can help to generate. Technologies are supportive to the extent that they provide an efficient means of handling (collect, store, and analyze) data, streamline processes (such as maintaining records, enrollment data and personnel information), monitor the use of resources, and improve communication among stakeholders such as teachers, parents, and communities (Haddad & Jurich, 2002, p. 38; Piper et al., 2015, p.4).

4.3. Selection of research articles

For the subsequent literature review, several selection criteria were considered. With the objective to present an overview and to allow for some generalization, several studies were analyzed for each included technology; by skimming through search results, the most frequently studied technologies were chosen to identify the most commonly applied ones. Furthermore, in order to provide a comprehensive picture, large-scale projects and small-scale ICT-based initiatives targeted at different aspects within the education sector were included. To sensitize to varying conditions of education and ICT possibilities across LMICs, studies from several countries with a low or middle income status were chosen. Apart from case studies, the research includes general information on the use of ICTs in education. Among the articles which would contribute to the outlined intentions, recent ones were preferred for more recent insights. After finding suitable studies, the abstracts and conclusions were read for a final check on their appropriateness. In the search process, relevant terms and their respective synonyms were included. These terms included ICTs, education and developing countries. Web searches using Google and Google Scholar as well as electronic searches using ERIC, EBSCO, the University of Passau's catalogue InfoGuide, and the search portal Primo were used.

4.4. Existing initiatives and their impact

Worldwide, numerous ICT-based initiatives have been implemented in an effort to improve education. The following section will provide practical evidence from different contexts in order to understand how technologies are used and to assess their effectiveness to improve education in LMICs.

4.4.1. Laptop-based initiatives

In the field of computer related education initiatives, there has been a move from desktop computers to more mobile solutions. With the emergence of multi-media laptops, first laptop initiatives in education were launched in the 1990s in the United States, before gradually appearing in LMICs. Being more affordable, portable, and thus fit for frequent use, laptops are more suitable than school computer labs. Those can mostly not hold large class sizes and therefore tend to infrequent use (Apiola et al., 2011, pp. 1-2; Piper et al., 2015, pp. 1-3).

Many governments over the world began to implement laptop projects without knowledge of their impact (Barrera-Osorio and Leigh, 2009, p. 2-23; Bebell & O'Dwyer, 2010, pp. 4-5). As the laptops developed by the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) Media Lab are the most known, applied, and studied ones for education in the developing world, insights on them will be analyzed below. The *100 dollar laptop* (although finally sold at nearly 200 USD), or *One Laptop per Child* (OLPC) is a largescale project providing laptops to children and teachers for educational purposes. The initiative was started in 2007 to improve learning in developing regions. The so called *Xo Laptops* are sold in bulks to governments or Non-governmental organization (NGOs) and then distributed to schools. An important principle of OLPC is that the devices are designated to be owned by the children and meant for use at school as well as at home. The rugged, low-cost, low-power laptops are connected either through a local network or the internet. Although the focus of OLPC lies in the poorest areas, access to electricity is a precondition to receive the devices. Apart from a free open source content software and applications for activities such as writing, browsing, games, music, and memorizing, up to 200 e-books can be chosen to be installed. The initiative has the objective to allow for collaborative, joyful, and self-empowered learning. In spite of relatively high costs

and little empirical evidence of its effects, many countries have implemented the OLPC program (Cristia, Ibararán, Cueto, Santiago, & Severín, 2012, pp. 1-18).

In their large-scale randomized evaluation of the OPLC program, Cristia et al. (2012) analyzed its impact in primary schools in rural communities in Peru. Their study sample included 319 public schools with scarce access to technology. 15 months after the initiation, the authors compared treatment schools with OPLC deployment to control schools without the program. Impacts on language, mathematics, and cognitive skills as well as laptop use were examined by conducting personal interviews, written tests, and analyzing laptop logs. Upon evaluation, all participating schools reported to have computers whereas 54% of control schools did not have any computer. Students of the treatment group demonstrated competence in operating core applications such as word processing and information research (which was mostly conducted on the device itself as most schools did not have access to the internet). Despite the same extent of usage between boys and girls, gained skills and preferred applications differed. Boys made more use of listening to and creating music, whereas girls tended to focus on word processing, browser, and calculator. Furthermore, boys demonstrated a small but significantly higher performance in laptop skills. Although the Xo laptops were intended for additional use at home, 60% of the children had to leave them at school because of principals' and parents' concerns about laptop security. When asked if they had used computers in the previous week, a large difference between the treatment and control group could be identified. 82% of the treatment group reported use at school and 42% at home, whereas only 26% of control group students had used it at school and only 4% at home. In spite of the provision of e-books, reading habits did not change. No effects on enrollment rates or performance in math and language tests could be observed. However, the Raven's Progressive Matrices test revealed that cognitive skills of treatment students were increased. Their scores were 0.09 to 0.13 standard deviations higher than in the control group, statistically significant at the 10% level. The quality of instruction had not changed. This can be explained by poor teacher instruction on the usage of the technology. Instructions by the MIT Media Lab on classroom integration are scarce (Cristia, Ibararán, Cueto, Santiago, & Severín, 2012, pp. 1-18).

Another study examined the impact of the OLPC Initiative in primary schools in Rwanda from the teachers' viewpoint. It analyzed laptop usage, teachers' attitudes towards the

technology and their perceived impacts on students. Information was collected through group discussions including 28 teachers (50% male and female) from four public schools. Teachers saw the OLPC as positive but mainly as a successful computer literacy program. Improved student-centered, self-directed learning through independent information search and the use for English vocabularies and diction were appreciated. The devices were also used to support teaching, for example for practicing mathematics. However, several side effects were revealed. Some instructors claimed increased disruption by children. Due to their ability to search for information, some challenged the teacher's authority, perceiving them as redundant for instructions. Concerning the program's intentions, various shortcomings could be detected. Many teachers perceived themselves as the main users of laptops, using them to improve their own knowledge and researching for lessons. Moreover, only two of the four schools had adopted the OLPC-designated 1:1 ratio. One school had realized a 1:2 and the last school a 1:4 ratio. An intensive use in classes was therefore not always possible. Even where a 1:1 ratio had been achieved, big class sizes of about 50 students complicated an effective integration of laptops. Likewise, the prescribed laptop ownership was not enforced. Some teachers reported that laptops were owned by the schools, burdening teachers with responsibility for the equipment. This caused many of them to prohibit children to take the devices home. During the group discussions, frequently reported shortcomings of the project were linked to the OLPC implementation: Insufficient technical support, deficient digital content, unreliable access to electricity and internet, lack of teacher training on laptop usage, and poor curriculum integration. These shortcomings resulted in teachers' reluctance in applying them for instructions (Fajebe, Best, & Smyth, 2013, pp. 29-37).

In their OLPC case study from Papua New Guinea, Saxe and de Kirby (2017) address the frequent notion that insufficient consideration of the economic and cultural context during implementation is a major reason for the failure of computer-based education projects in developing countries. The authors focus on the actions of involved individuals and the provoking conditions. They argue that while proponents might take supportive actions, others could initiate interventions that threaten the program. The underlying case study analyzed the progression of the OLPC program initiated in 2010 in remote, poor communities in Papua New Guinea. Access to technology was scarce, with the first cellphones arriving only in 2011. A process approach is applied to examine the evolution of the initiative, revealing how under changing circumstances perceived threats to the

project were created or resolved by actions of different stakeholders, before the project came to a hold by 2014. To understand the progress and underlying events, direct observations of and conversations with OLPC involved individuals (especially teachers, headmasters, volunteers and technical support), analysis of records, stories of community members, and video documentations of OLPC training sessions were undertaken.

In the examined project, 385 Xo laptops with solar panels as power source were distributed to three primary schools. The sponsoring organization was the NGO Papua New Guinea Sustainable Development Program (PNGSDP) that was responsible for the funding, implementation, and support of this initiative. In an initial phase, the laptops were productively used by students and teachers. By 2014, they were hardly used and many devices had disappeared into the community. One aspect for the failure of the OLPC initiative is ascribed to the scarce prior contact to technology. The laptops were perceived as alien and teacher training was unexpectedly difficult. This required not only workshops on how to integrate the laptops in the curriculum, but also an intensive introduction to basic functions. Limited teacher skills on usage contributed to laptops being abandoned. Furthermore, religious concerns arose, as laptops were thought to be a source of evil, worrying some parents to let their children go to school. While a pastor spread his concerns regarding this, an engaged headmaster promoted the devices' advantages. Because of the poor economy, the envisioned laptop ownership by children produced security concerns, moving one of the three headmasters to keep the devices at school, whereas students from the other schools were allowed to take them home. Where ownership by children was pursued, a large number of laptops disappeared into the community where the solar panels were used to charge cellphones, or laptops exchanged for cash. The density of devices at these schools decreased to a point that made classroom-intensive work with them impossible. The headmaster of the school which had not allowed to take the devices home had successfully preserved intensive pedagogical integration of the laptops at his school. But when he was transferred to another school in 2012, the low laptop density at his new school impeded him to promote their intensive use. At his old school, the laptops were not used because the new headmaster was not acquainted with them. A decisive event for the resumption of the initiative was the nationalization of the funding organization PNGSDP in 2012. This consequently ended professional support and the delivery of additionally needed devices. As teachers would have needed continuous refreshing trainings, its discontinuation contributed to

an abandoning of the technology. In this OLPC case with tough starting conditions, providing initial trainings and support was not sufficient to successfully continue the program (Saxe & de Kirby, 2017, pp. 2-17).

Apiola et al. (2011) likewise report that many researchers criticize the focus of most one-to-one computer initiatives on the device and admonish that impacts on education require pedagogical and curriculum considerations. The authors faced a similar situation in a primary school in Iringa, Tanzania, where 100 Xo laptops had been distributed in 2009. The mostly computer illiterate teachers had not received training or guidelines on how to use the laptops and as a consequence, they were hardly used. Through their study, the authors show that with sufficient consideration of pedagogical approaches, the devices can contribute to improve students' learning outcomes and working styles.

In their five months research experiment between 2010 and 2011, local and foreign teachers jointly designed a pedagogical approach that considered the local educational context, teacher experience as well as theoretical literature on one-to-one computer use at school. During the study period of five months, a target group of 56 grade seven students participated in two workshops per week. Eventually, teaching students how to use different applications, guiding them on how to search for information about specific questions, integrating the teacher role as a facilitator, and combining lecture sessions with group projects resulted in remarkable success. Interviews with teachers and quizzes with students were conducted to gain information on difficulties and impacts of the laptop project. As a first obstacle, teachers revealed that contents on the devices needed to be translated to the local language as many students did not understand the English study materials. Furthermore, for security reasons, laptops were kept in storage rooms. As the school did not have its own facility, the devices needed to be deposited at a distant place. Hence, teachers needed to transport the laptops to school, resulting in a suboptimal student to computer ratio as not all laptops could be brought to classrooms. Moreover, the unreliability of electricity supply impeded the possibility of charging the devices as needed. However, overall the participants were content about the benefits of the laptops. Quizzes demonstrated that knowledge on topics taught by the developed method substantially improved. Student motivation and problem solving skills were increased. Although the authors agree to the widespread criticism on the necessity of an appropriate pedagogical approach, they do not support the claim that

these guidelines should be provided by the OLPC foundation. They suggest that appropriate pedagogical methods depend on the context and thus need to be developed by locals (Apiola, Pakarinen, & Tedre, 2011, pp. 1-7).

A study on Mongolia's OLPC experience also indicates that by adopting a holistic strategy, student achievements can be improved. Yamaguchi et al. (2014) analyzed the effects of the OLPC implementation in primary schools and found that students' reading – albeit not mathematical – skills enhanced. In 2008, the OLPC foundation donated laptops to the Mongolian government with the objective to equip all grade 2 to 5 students with a computer and install a high speed information technology (IT) network supplying all schools by 2015. A total of 12.100 laptops was distributed to students and teachers in 43 schools. A holistic strategy was pursued and the OLPC Project Organizing Committee (PMU) established to facilitate the nationwide project. By the end of 2010, several supportive measures were applied by the PMU, including basic rules and responsibilities such as for the coverage of internet connection fees, agreements with parents, responsibilities on laptop delivery, and technical maintenance support for schools. Furthermore, local networking and power supply were expanded, a content framework for each grade defined, monitoring visits to schools organized, and teachers trained on the use of the devices. In 2013 the authors evaluated the initiative's impact on children's literacy and mathematical skills. The study assessed the performance of 2011 grade 5 students from seven OLPC and seven non-OLPC primary schools in different regions of Mongolia. Questionnaires were used to gather information on students' computer use and their attitude towards them. The authors applied a difference-in-difference approach with a control and treatment group to assess the technology's impact on student achievements over time and on the achievements of OLPC vs. non-OLPC students.

For the evaluation of the initiative's impact on reading and mathematics achievements, the authors used test score points from National Assessment Tests instead of percentages as indicators. First, the authors determined performance differences at baseline between the Non-OLPC and OLPC group, revealing a net-difference of 1.81 points for math and 0.03 for reading. After adjusting for the initial differences, the results showed that the OLPC initiative had not affected skills in math but had a statistically significant positive impact on reading skills, inducing a difference of 3.75 points between OLPC

compared to non-OLPC schools in 2012. In treatment schools, the project had a net effect of 17% on reading scores comparing the achievements of 2008 and 2012. Net effect of laptop use on reading scores was determined through a multivariate regression in which independent variables were introduced stepwise. With a significance at 0.05, the model explained 30.6% of variations in reading scores. It showed that the OLPC had a significant net effect on reading achievements controlling for gender, math score, and hours spent for watching television, doing homework, and earning money. Moreover, the model found that math skills, time of watching television and doing homework increased reading skills, whereas earning money decreased reading scores. Girls had on average significantly higher reading scores than boys (Yamaguchi, Sukhbaatar, Takada, & Dayan-Ochir, 2014, pp. 89-99).

The discussed initiatives give an insight into how differently one-to-one laptop initiatives across LMICs have been implemented, and that impacts of the same technology on learning vary. Researchers claim that there is little affirmative evidence on the success of such initiatives. The rising investment in ICT-use in education that is pursued by many developing countries is based on beliefs rather than facts: That modern ICTs will improve quality of instruction and increase efficiency, motivation, and student skills (Barrera-Osorio and Leigh, 2009, p. 2-23; Bebell & O'Dwyer, 2010, pp. 4-5). In spite of the scarce evidence base, investments in laptop-based education initiatives are expanding. The MIT Media Lab alone has distributed 3 million laptops worldwide (OLPC, 2018).

4.4.2. *Tablet-based initiatives*

Tablets are among the most recent technologies introduced to classrooms for educational purposes. They are similar to laptops although even more portable. Reliable findings on their impact on student performance are barely available and yet, governments are increasingly supporting large-scale tablet initiatives in education. Governments' support of tablet initiatives is typically not based on evidence but on assumptions on improved access to content, social inclusion, and independent learning. Cost analyses are often not conducted in advance and questions on procurement and organizational models not considered. As a new technology, tablets are producing the same hype in the education sector as laptops did (Tamim et al., 2015, pp. 3-25; Piper et al., 2015, pp. 3-4; Viriyapong & Harfield, 2013, p. 176-177). Currently, most findings of studies on the use

of tablets in education stem from high income countries where teachers and children are already used to the technology, and where electricity and internet coverage are given (Clarke & Svanaes, 2014). Nevertheless, a few studies exist on the introduction of tablets in developing countries. The following section will focus on such initiatives.

Conducting a case study on Thailand's nationwide *One Tablet per Child* (OTPC) initiative, Viriyapong & Harfield (2013) detect the main challenges arising in this large-scale educational tablet project and provide solutions. In 2012, the Ministry of Education in Thailand began to provide all class one primary school children with a tablet to improve education and access to learning resources especially in remote areas, and distributed 800.000 tablets. It is the worldwide largest project providing tablets to students. The devices contain 336 preloaded learning objects, including e-books, videos, and interactive content. In addition, schools can load extra applications. The Thai Ministry of Education focuses on the provision and maintenance of tablets, leaving it to schools to develop tablet usage policies and to determine the scope and types of applied activities.

Through classroom observations and discussions with teachers, four areas of challenges in the OTPC project were identified: Contextualized content, usability, assessment of student achievements, and teacher support. In view of content, the authors report the importance to adapt learning materials to local contexts as differences in culture, language and educational competency of teachers exist across the country. Aspects of usability referred to the observation that a certain degree of interactivity and sufficient depth of activities was needed in order to obtain children's motivation and achieve positive effects on learning outcomes. As children progress at different paces in solving tasks on their tablets, the evaluation of learning outcomes is another important aspect. Tablet activities should collect data on children's performance to help teachers to identify students who require further support. In addition, lesson plans need to relate curriculum goals to specific tablet activities to inform teachers on the class's progression. In regard to teacher training, complaints were raised that teachers should also receive tablets to allow for adequate lesson preparation and to deliver clear instructions to teachers on the integration of tablets in classroom activities.

With the objective to develop better solutions, the authors undertook a case study by developing science activities for first grade students that took the identified issues into consideration. The case study involved three primary schools and was divided into the

stages content development, implementation of activities and the underlying infrastructure, as well as testing of learning materials in classrooms. Designing the activities involved teachers and was based on contents of local text books to ensure contextualized content. Moreover, lesson plans were created to ensure a direct link to grade-specific learning outcomes. Each activity consisted of teaching, examples, and exercises with integrated correction. For the collection of data on student performance, an offline solution was developed due to the unreliable internet connection. Student tablets stored data on their progress on a local database. As soon as a connection was available, data was transferred to a cloud-based server from which teachers could access analyses. This data helped teachers to identify student's performance and areas of general difficulties that require further explanations.

After designing the activities, they were tested in two phases. In a preliminary test, the programs were tested by grades one and two students in two small schools of 12-20 children. Researchers detected program shortcomings by observing children. After modifying the content, a second test was conducted in a third school with 20 grade one students. In this test, tablet data and observations of children solving tasks were collected to verify improvements and appropriate support by teachers. Eventually, redesigning activities thoughtfully could improve tablet usability and solve technical as well as content related issues. By including evaluation of data on student performance, pedagogical difficulties were decreased and student motivation as well as their need for support improved (Viriyapong & Harfield, 2013, pp. 176-183).

A tablet-based education initiative from Malawi indicates that tablets with carefully designed applications have the potential to improve student achievements. Concerned about high dropout rates, low basic skills, the lack of teaching and learning materials as well as of qualified teachers, the Ministry of Education, Science and Technology decided to introduce the mobile technology initiative *oneclass* across 68 primary schools in a pilot phase. Funds were provided by the international charity Voluntary Service Overseas (VSO), the Royal Norwegian Embassy in Malawi, the Scottish government, and the UK's Department for International Development. In collaboration with VSO and the charity *onebillion*, the participating classes were provided with a learning center and interactive apps that were integrated into mathematics and literacy education. The

learning centers were specially designed classrooms equipped with solar power to enable the use of the apps in areas where reliable power coverage is not given. The apps were delivered through iPad minis connected to headphones and teachers received trainings on dealing with the technology. In their study, Hubber et al. (2016) focused on math skills of primary school students and examined if tablets enhanced educational achievements. The authors considered a math app that instructs students by means of a virtual teacher in the local language through activities that are aligned to the national curriculum. By monitoring app-records, teachers were informed on students' performance to dedicate special attention to children with difficulties. As teaching was mostly provided by the app, high-quality mathematics education was delivered to classes even if the teacher skills were low.

From September to November 2013, the authors conducted a randomized controlled trial including 283 primary school students in classes one to three in a medium sized urban school. After a period of eight weeks, comparisons between participating and control classes showed that the use of tablets had improved conceptual mathematics knowledge of children by 4% and curriculum knowledge by 18%. A difference between genders could not be found, although previously boys had commonly performed better than girls. Moreover, class attendance in the treatment group improved as children's engagement increased. Based on these findings, the authors conclude that tablets can be applied in developing contexts to replace missing high-quality content and teaching. In April of 2017, the Ministry of Education announced to take over ownership of the project and to integrate it into the National Education Policy Framework to ensure its sustainability. By 2018, the project's scale has increased and is reaching up to 90.000 children (Hubber, Outhwaite, Chigeda, McGrath, Hodgen, & Pitchford, 2016, pp. 1-3; Pitchford, 2015, pp. 1-9; VSO, 2018).

In Kenya, the government's Primary Math and Reading Initiative (PRIMR) tested and evaluated different tablet initiatives in schools to determine their effectiveness regarding student achievements and costs. The PRIMR, developed by the Ministry of Education, Science and Technology (MoEST) and the USAID in 2011, is a program to identify ways to improve instruction and to enhance literacy and numeracy skills of children in grades one and two. It forms part of the effort to decrease educational disadvantages for girls and rural children. Piper et al. (2015) summarize the impact of three PRIMR initiatives

on student performance and their cost effectiveness. Randomized controlled trials were conducted for three projects in which e-readers for students in grades one and two, tablets for teachers, and tablets for the Teachers' Advisory Centre (TAC) were tested. The programs were conducted in 20 randomly selected semi-urban and rural schools in Kenya's Kismu County. For the PRIMR study, baseline and final literacy assessments were conducted in three treatment groups and one control group in January and October of 2013. As baseline skills in the four groups were not equivalent, a difference-indifference approach was applied to analyze the program impact. One of the three treatment groups was equipped with Kindle e-readers for every child and teacher. They contained a variety of reading materials in English, Kiswahili, and the local language. In the teacher tablet initiative, Google Nexus tablets complemented classroom instructions. The tablets contained multimedia lesson plans, pedagogical support, sound-practice capabilities, and a student assessment program that provided advice on which lessons to reemphasize. For the third version, Google Nexus tablets with advice on teacher support were provided to teacher supervisors. These TAC tutors in turn were supported by the PRIMR technical team.

Evaluating student performance after the initiatives showed that in all three versions, children's literacy skills had statistically significantly improved. A comparison between the three groups revealed that the TAC tutor tablet had been most effective in enhancing achievements, followed by the teacher tablet, and finally the e-reader program. In order to determine cost effectiveness, implementation cost of the PRIMR initiatives were compared to those of typical literacy programs in Kenya. The cost difference was then divided by the unit cost per student for each treatment group. This analysis demonstrated that again, the TAC teacher tablets were most effective, followed by the teacher tablets, and lastly e-readers. The authors suggest that especially for the mostly rural schools in Kenya where teacher quality is low, PRIMR's program could be scaled up using the TAC tutor tablets, as they are most effective in regards to cost and impact (Piper, Jepkemie, Kwayumba, & Kibukho, 2015, pp. 3-11). This test project shows that tablet initiatives can be successfully implemented at different school levels and demonstrates the importance of teacher support and cost analysis in ICT initiatives.

Nedugundi et al. (2018) report on a different approach of introducing tablets in rural Indian schools. As common in many developing countries, teachers in Indian rural

schools are usually poorly qualified, payed, and motivated. Lack of teachers and teacher absenteeism are serious consequences. To address these problems, the authors investigated how the implementation of WhatsApp for remote teacher monitoring and of further apps delivered on tablets to support educational improvements could decrease teacher and student absenteeism and enhance student performance.

The examined initiative provided tablets to teachers to send their daily attendance status and lesson content as well as periodic performance reports to a monitoring team via WhatsApp groups. As the ownership and use of social media in rural India is rising and becoming common, this technology appeared to be appropriate. In order to ensure an adequate use by all teachers, a training on the use of tablets was conducted at the beginning of the project. For the attendance status, teachers took time stamped pictures along with their students at the beginning and end of each class. In addition, apps for student attendance and assessment were introduced. Tablets were also used for continuous teacher training. Teachers shared experiences via WhatsApp and shared a teaching video once per month. Based on this, central coordinators and other teachers helped planning lessons and provided feedback on teachers' instructions. In addition, educational apps and videos for classroom activities developed for rural Indian contexts were sent to teachers via WhatsApp. As the messages were sent in group chats that could be seen by other teachers, community pressure motivated teachers to perform well.

The analysis was based on WhatsApp chats over a period of nine months involving 26 participants (8968 messages). Furthermore, data from the monitoring app and on student assessments was evaluated. This analysis revealed that the frequency of interaction between teachers and coordinators had a significant positive effect on teacher attendance. Moreover, student attendance, instructional quality, and student performance improved (Nedungadi, Mulik, & Raman, 2018, pp. 117-125).

Overall, it seems that factors for success are similar to those of laptop initiatives. As the similarity of the technologies may suggest, the findings replicate insights from laptop-based initiatives in education. Nevertheless, due to their higher mobility and appropriateness of interactive apps, tablets provide some different possibilities.

4.4.3. *Mobile phone-based initiatives*

Even in remote areas of low income countries, the penetration and use of mobile phones is widespread and increasing. Various education enhancing efforts are utilizing this development to deploy solutions that are making use of mobile phones. Although most of the projects are of a small scope, they are inclusive, scalable, and present promising outcomes. In the following, some *mEducation* projects, as they are called, will be presented (Aker et al., 2012, p. 118; Kaleebu, Gee, Maybanks, Jones, & Watson, 2013, pp. 50-51; STOA, 2015, p. 10; Trucano, 2015, p. 63; Watson, 2015).

Kaleebu et al. (2013) report a mobile phone based project implemented in Papua New Guinea that aimed at orienting and motivating teachers. The *SMS Story* project sent daily SMSs to grade one and two teachers consisting of short stories and lesson plans with the objective to improve students' reading abilities. The initiative was introduced in rural, remote primary schools where the educational environment is challenging due to remoteness, poverty, high illiteracy, linguistic diversity, low teacher quality, and lack of education material. Because of the linguistic diversity, the government had decided to make English the future language of instruction (Kaleebu et al., 2013, pp. 50-59). Although in rural areas basic communication devices such as newspapers, television, and fixed phones are rare, mobile phones are widely accessible. The mobile network coverage has spread since 2007 and among teachers involved in this study, 91.9% owned mobile phones (Kaleebu et al. 2013, p. 52; Watson, 2015, p. 141; World Bank Group, 2016, p. 146).

The project was initiated by the VSO in 2013. This case study analyzes learning outcomes and presents lessons learnt from the project. The researchers applied a controlled trial with a treatment and control group to find out whether the project could improve reading skills of students. Over a period of 20 weeks, 57 teachers from 20 primary schools in the treatment group received one SMS with a short story and one SMS comprising a lesson plan every school day morning. The provision of stories compensated for the lack of schoolbooks. Instead of a direct training, teachers received cartoon-based instructions on the steps they should follow every day. Control group teachers were given an unrelated mathematics pack. The nearly 2.500 students of both groups were assessed in their reading skills at the beginning and end of the study. Reading abilities at baseline were equal in both groups with no differences between genders. Additional information

for the evaluation of the project were collected through teacher interviews, observations of lessons and student workbooks. All teachers properly received and used the SMS stories for teaching. Charging the phones appeared to be the only difficulty for teachers, as not all of them had an own facility to charge the batteries. However, those affected payed to get them charged and the low cost burden did not prevent any teacher from continuing their participation (Kaleebu et al., 2013, pp. 50-59). A comparison of students' reading abilities at the end of the study revealed that those in the treatment group were significantly higher than those in the control group. This positive result demonstrates that an adequate strategic use of mobile phones can contribute to improve education. Project cost were low as no face-to-face teacher training was necessary and the devices used did not have to be provided (Watson, 2015, pp. 143-147).

Another study by Aker et al. (2012) found that the mere ability to use mobile phones can enhance education outcomes of mostly illiterate people. The authors evaluated results from the adult education project *Program Alphabétisation de Base par Cellulaire* (Program ABC) which was established between 2009 and 2010 in Niger. In a randomized controlled trial, 113 rural villages were divided into two groups. Both groups of villages received the same curriculum during a course of 8 months with 15 hours per week, and half of the randomly chosen villages additionally obtained a mobile phone component during class time. This program taught students basic instructions on phone usage such as sending SMS and conducting calls, and provided each 5-people group of literacy classes with one mobile phone. Being able to use SMS or making calls allowed students in ABC villages to practice their skills. In total, 5.600 students were involved.

Baseline analyses were conducted in order to allow for a difference-in-difference specification. Literacy and numeracy skills between the two groups were comparable at baseline and merely existent. At the end of the course period, tests were absolved. Both the standard and ABC groups had advanced in math and writing skills and achieved a first grade level in writing and a second grade level in mathematics. Comparing the groups, test scores in ABC villages were by 13% for writing and 8% for math higher than in the standard villages, with statistically significant results. No differences in terms of gender or age were found. Seven months after course end, an unannounced test was performed to identify skill depreciation. Writing and math scores fell in both groups, but less so in ABC villages. Z-scores for writing skills were 0.13 standard deviations higher in the ABC

group, however not at a statistically significant level. For math performance, the difference was statistically significant at a 5% level and by 0.19 standard deviations higher for ABC participants. This shows that the effect of the ABC program persisted. This initiative is easily scalable from an infrastructural as well as cost view, as mobile phone coverage is widespread in most contexts where literacy and numeracy skills are scarce (Aker et al., 2012, p. 118; World Bank Group, 2016, p. 146).

A similar study on a literacy and mathematics adult education program in rural Nigerian villages examines whether monitoring teachers has an effect on learning outcomes and teacher absenteeism. Teacher absenteeism poses a challenge in education in Niger. Teacher monitoring is difficult because of a limited infrastructure and weak institutions. The underlying project was implemented by a NGO between 2014 and 2016 and provided 10 months of literacy and numeracy course of 15 hours per week. Aker and Ksoll (2017) evaluate the potential of mobile phone-based teacher monitoring, enabling regular communication between governments or organizations and remote areas, as a low-cost remedy for teacher absenteeism.

In this study, a randomized controlled trial with three groups was conducted. 131 villages were divided into one village group that received the standard education program, one that additionally received a monitoring program, and a control group without any intervention involving 20 villages. In the monitoring villages, data collection agents performed weekly calls to two students, the village chief, and the teacher to acquire information on class regularity and student attendance. The mobile phones were already owned by villagers. No formal sanctions or financial incentives were applied. In the second year, the monitoring component was reduced to only calling the teacher.

Analyses of test scores at baseline showed that literacy and numeracy skills were similar between all groups, with men scoring higher than women in all villages. Over the two year course, average test scores in the standard education group increased z-scores by 0.14-0.30 standard deviations for reading and 0.13-0.29 standard deviations for math compared to the pure control group. Comparing the monitoring villages to the standard education group, the test scores for reading were higher by 0.07-0.19 standard deviations and those for math by 0.07-0.12 standard deviations. These differences were comparable between genders and statistically significant.

Evaluating learning gains over time, the coefficients for the learning gains of the monitoring initiative were still large but lost significance. The authors conclude that maintaining the full monitoring program was necessary to keep up enough community pressure to continue the same level of improvement in learning. Contrary to the authors' expectations, no significant influence on teacher absenteeism could be found and reported reasons for their absence were mostly illness, funerals, and agricultural work. An increase in the motivation of teachers or students could not be determined. However, attrition was lower in the monitoring villages, indicating a higher dedication. As the mobile monitoring component increased student performance, the authors reason that the program might have enhanced teachers' and students' class preparation. In view of the positive effect on literacy and numeracy skills, this study indicates that mobile phone technology can be used as a cost effective tool to improve learning outcomes of students in poor countries (Aker & Ksoll, 2017, pp. 1-27).

The discussed implementations demonstrate that mobile phones offer various possibilities to support education, from the provision of content and lesson plans to teacher monitoring and the opportunity to practice skills. Additionally, they are also used in the educational system. For example, administrative failures such as delays and corruption lead to inadequate systems for the payment of teacher salaries. Payroll using money transfer services can improve reliability of teacher compensation and thus increase their motivation and incentives to teach. Although not every teacher has a bank account, mobile phones are common even in remote areas. Also, the distance to a mobile network is often closer than to the next bank or to travel to meet the responsible person to get the salary in cash. Thus, the use of mobile payment programs is expanding and already common in many LMICs (Monks, 2017; Trucano, 2014, pp. 37-42; UNESCO, 2017a, p. 268). Furthermore, mobile phones offer an attractive alternative to heavily paper-based means of data collection. Data on education projects such as the progress of school constructions can be shared faster, cheaper, and with higher data accuracy as transcription errors can be avoided. The free SMS-based tool U-report which has been developed by UNICEF Uganda for example is used to establish transparency on education related project funds and to monitor the supply and use of learning materials (Trucano, 2015, pp. 63-71). Mobile phones are suitable for such undertakings as they are readily available and as systems for data collection can be designed for the use on simple devices.

4.4.4. Broadcasting-based initiatives

Similar to mobile phones, radio and television are widespread in most regions of LMICs. In case of the radio, not even reliable supply of electricity is required as battery-based radios are common. Radio and television can be used to deliver educational material and reach geographically remote, culturally disadvantaged or working population that cannot attend traditional education, and are therefore especially relevant for distance learning. Connection to the internet or digital literacy are not necessary. Theoretically, a large audience within the reception area can be reached if the language requirements fit. As the necessary hardware is usually already in place, relatively low cost initiatives can be realized. However, broadcasting faces several constraints in delivering education. As broadcast schedules are predetermined, asynchronous learning is not possible (unless recorded). In such cases, broadcasting the same content several times can allow for some flexibility. If the educational program is limited to the application of broadcasting the direction is one-way. The reception is transient and listening or watching students cannot go back in the lecture to repeat insufficiently understood parts. Although pedagogical possibilities are limited, they can be combined with other mediums or be used to complement class room instruction (Haddad, pp. 4-6; Nettleton, 1991, pp. 111-112).

First extensive ICT-based education programs used broadcasting. Ethiopia began its first distance learning program relying on the use of radio broadcast in 1967. They were targeted at adults who could not attend secondary education. During the 1990s the Educational Media Agency (EMA) introduced Interactive Radio Instruction programs (IRI programs) to increase student enrolment at primary levels and to lower the drop-out rates. To reach these goals, the quality of education and teacher skills should be improved. To improve teacher skills and efficiently reach nationwide teachers, a distance learning initiative financed by the USAID was initiated. Radio-based lectures were complemented by face-to-face tutorials that were to attend every six weeks. Tutors regularly corrected assignments and provided the teachers with printing materials. To improve student achievements, IRI programs were designed to complement classroom instructions and make lessons more interactive, student centered, and enhance education quality. The project focused on English skills and provided 15 minute programs which included instructions for teachers on its usage. Exercises, cassettes, and print material completed the lectures. Regular student assessments were conducted to ensure program quality.

Between January and June 2001 an experimental research was conducted in eight schools in different regions to assess the impact of the IRI on English skills in primary schools. The analysis included data from observations, reports, and group discussions including parents, teachers, and community representatives. English skills of students in IRI and non-IRI classes were compared by conducting English comprehension tests. Learning outcomes were positively affected, with 22% gains in English skills in participating compared to 9% in non-IRI classes. Female students performed on average higher than male, and performance gaps between different age groups were decreased. Learning gains in rural and urban schools were equal, and learning gain differences based on teacher skills eliminated. Additionally, the program improved teachers' development as they learned new strategies of instruction and enhance their English skills by listening to the audios. Group discussions indicated that students' cognitive development had also increased (Nekatibeb & Tilson, 2004, pp. 123-138).

Evidence from worldwide IRI programs confirm positive outcomes. Furthermore, a common finding is that skill gaps between rural and urban students as well as between genders were successfully diminished. Some IRI programs reach up to a million students per program (for example in Guinea, the nationwide IRI program is used in nearly all primary schools), whereas other IRI programs focus on a smaller audience in areas with multiple languages and ethnic groups. Apart from improving student performance, IRI projects across Africa, Asia, and Latin America tend to endure. Of 30 large initiatives, about 2/3 still formed a critical part of formal and non-formal education systems 25 years after take-up (Bosch, 2004, pp. 149-162; Bosch, Rhodes, & Kariuki, 2002, pp. 135-137).

Bosch (2004) analyzes factors that impeded the success of terminated IRI initiatives. Outstanding reasons for IRI failures were inadequate programs, recurrent cost, poor institutionalization, insufficient local ownership or changes in policies and in political leadership. The author points out that especially in the initial phase program impacts need to be evaluated in order to detect weaknesses. As changes in educational trends occur over time, programs should be regularly updated. To ensure program sustainability, strategies to deal with costs arising from airtime, power supplies, and continuous teacher training need to be developed. These can be based on taxes, agreements between ministries of education and communication, long-term contracts with radio sta-

tions, or school sponsorships. If education initiatives are not institutionalized, a drawback of the initiating organization can result in the termination of the program. Likewise, changes in administration or educational policies alter the framework of education systems, possibly leading to a decentralization of education, privatization of communication systems, and eventually loss of political support. New agreements, ways of financing, and leaderships need to be established to ensure a continuation. For countries with scarce financial means and a poor infrastructure, IRI programs are attractive as they constitute a cost efficient option to enhance educational quality and access (Bosch, 2004, pp. 149-162).

Television is another longer established technology and has been applied in different educational contexts. Although using television for educational purpose is more expensive than using the radio, it is still more widespread in poor communities than modern ICTs and its visual character provides more pedagogical possibilities than the radio. In an initial phase of enthusiasm, various television-based education initiatives were supported by aid organizations. However, as a large audience is required to cover the costs and evidence on its educational advantages concerning learning outcomes compared to radio courses remained unclear, investments in this technology by international organizations decreased in the 1980s. Distance learning initiatives that rely on broadcasting usually reach those belonging to a major language. This constitutes an advantage in Latin America as compared to Asian or African countries (Rodriguez, 2011, p. 2). The pronounced television culture in Latin American countries with only two major languages, Spanish and Portuguese, presents a great opportunity for television-based education projects (Heyneman & Haynes, 2004, p. 62).

In 2000, the television-based education initiative *Telecurso* was implemented in Brazil. It was developed by two private television networks, *The Global Network* and the *Robert Maerinho Foundation*, to target high school drop-outs and enable young adults to complete secondary education. Film makers, universities, schools, and foundations jointly developed high quality televised programs for basic and secondary education. Special centers provided teachers for support and allowed students to take their exam in their rural village (Rodriguez, 2011, pp. 4-7). In order to reach young workers, students can acquire tapes if they cannot watch the televised classes at broadcasting time. Evidence from studies indicate that learning outcomes of *Telecurso* students are higher than from

regular education. Because of their high quality, materials from *Telecurso* are also used by public schools (Heyneman & Haynes, 2004, p. 62).

A successful example for television-based efforts to promote gender equality and improve females' standing in education is the series *Alam Simsim* in Egypt. This co-production of *Sesame Street* was developed by USAID and Cairo's Education and Training Program to influence low primary school enrollment, low school performance especially among girls, and modest literacy rates among women. Basic numeracy and literacy skills among Egyptian children are especially rudimentary in rural Upper Egypt. However, even in rural regions television ownership is high, with a national penetration rate of 96%, making television an appropriate technology to reach a large audience. With a curious female Muppet as a main character and presenting "girls as active, equal participants", *Alam Simsim* encourages a change in gender based attitudes of children and parents (Ward-Brent, 2002, p. 156). The program provides a format that is attractive for the whole family and was first aired in 2000. In 2001, it was already regularly watched countrywide by 96% and 86% of children under age eight in urban and rural regions respectively as well as 54% of mothers. Research on the series' impact has shown that gender related views among children who regularly watched the series were changing (Ward-Brent, 2002, pp. 154-157).

The largest ICT project in education is a mainly television-based initiative from China. From 2003 to 2007, China implemented its *Distance Education Project for Rural Schools* (DEPRS) as part of the country's effort to universalize basic education in rural areas. After two successful pilot programs, the State Council approved the construction of DEPRS as a nationwide rural distance learning network. The central government provided 12 billion Chinese Renminbi Yuan (CNY) for this purpose (1.45 billion USD at 2004 exchange rates). Targeting different educational levels, three delivery models were developed (McQuaide, 2009, pp. 1-5; National Bureau of Statistics China, 2015, chapter 19-8).

The related responsibility for regulation and guidance was given to regional offices. The first model aimed at the 110.000 rural elementary schools in small villages which comprised grades one through three. These schools were provided with DVDs, a DVD player, and a television set. Apart from students, teachers were to benefit from the program by acquiring better teaching methods. The second model was developed for the 384.000 intermediate schools in large villages and townships which covered classes one to six. In

addition to model one, it included satellite technology for televised broadcasts which were provided by the education channel of the Chinese Central Television. The third model, for 37.500 junior high schools, was equipped as the second model, but additionally with computer rooms which provided high-speed internet and multi-media classrooms in order to enable the download of online and web-based materials. The second and third models were furthermore supported by *Air Classroom*, a daily aired program by the education channel of the Chinese Central Television.

By 2007, 80% of China's rural schools had received the program implementation. Although statistical data on student examination is not available, there have been evaluations of DEPRS's impact on student performance. One evaluation was performed on an English learning initiative that was based on the DEPRS infrastructure. In 2005, the Provincial Education Province in the Hubei Province in Central China decided that all students should learn English from grade three on. Many of the 16.000 schools faced the challenge of teacher shortage and low quality of the available English teachers. The DEPRS infrastructure was used to solve this difficulty. Where English teachers were not skilled, the provincial television education channel and DVD broadcast station provided instructional supplements, and where teachers were not available, they substituted them. The courses were developed by a British expert and Chinese educators, and teacher trainings on how to implement the courses were integrated. During the observation period 2005 to 2007, all rural elementary schools in the region used this program for English lessons. An evaluation from 2007 by several national education institutions found that DERPS had enabled access to English lessons to four million rural students with high achievements in pronunciation and conversational abilities.

The findings indicate that DEPRS has a high potential to improve education in rural areas of China. However, it also faces challenges. Critics lament that the central government's financing of the infrastructure only covered one third of the total project costs. Additional recurrent costs for personnel, maintenance of equipment, teacher trainings, and operation need to be borne by local governments. However, 84% of the rural schools using DERPS are located in relatively poor western regions, such that some schools could not afford the second and third models. Another critic regards the many ethnic minority groups within rural regions with specific cultures and customs. They tend to dislike the courses as they lack reference to their history (McQuaide, 2009, pp. 9-15).

5. Success factors of effective use of ICTs in education

As the overview of ICT-initiatives for educational purposes has shown, large differences do exist regarding applied technologies, prospects, targeted objectives, project scope, required infrastructure as well as prerequisites. In how far do ICTs contribute to the SDG 4? What are the crucial success factors of ICT-initiatives? What are the barriers for their implementation in LMICs? The following section will try to summarize answers.

5.1. Contribution of ICTs to the SDG 4

In the *Incheon Declaration of 2015*, several approaches have been identified in order to tackle the learning crisis. In the context of primary and secondary education they focus on the sub-ordinate targets **access, inclusion, and gender equality** as well as **quality**.

With respect to **access** to education, IRI programs worldwide have helped to increase enrolment at the primary and secondary level. The print-material and tutorial combined IRI program in Ethiopia has been used to improve skills of nationwide teachers. The television aided *Telecurso* in Brazil facilitated access to secondary education to students that could otherwise not achieve this educational level. DEPRS in China has brought English classes to rural schools, even where English teachers were not available. Large distance learning infrastructures could also be useful in situations where face-to-face instruction is not possible or temporarily interrupted when schools close for reasons such as conflicts, environmental disasters or epidemics.

With respect to **inclusion and gender equality**, ICT-initiatives have shown to be successful. Apart from providing access to education to those affected by exterior influences, distance learning benefits the population that is disadvantaged due to physical disabilities, ethnicity or gender. Several projects have proven to decrease or eliminate educational achievement gaps between male and female students as well as urban and rural ones. For example, the television program *Alam Simsim* in Egypt has diminished the culture-based bias against females in education. The tablet initiative *oneclass* in Malawi has eliminated gender-based differences in math skills for students. Likewise, mobile phone based literacy and numeracy programs in Niger removed the usual differences in educational skills between male and female villagers. Worldwide IRI programs have balanced learning gains between urban and rural schools as well as between genders.

Quality is determined by many factors, thus, most of the evidence on the impact of ICT-initiatives relates to this category. For example, OLPC in Rwanda has facilitated class preparation for teachers, motivated students to study independently and to use new methods to practice English. In Mongolia, the large-scale laptop-initiative has enhanced reading skills of students. A case study on the use of tablets in Thai primary schools has demonstrated how student assessment can be performed efficiently and activities be designed in a way that motivates children. Introducing high-quality apps on tablets in Malawi grew class attendance of students, their engagement, and math skills considerably. Testing several tablet-based projects in Kenya has shown that lesson planning, instructional quality, and student performance can easily be improved. In Papua New Guinea, a SMS-based project has demonstrated that simple mobile phones can mitigate the lack of school books and improve classroom instruction. Mobile phones in a literacy and numeracy course in Niger enhanced student achievements by allowing to practice in everyday situations. Likewise, using mobile phones for teacher monitoring improved student performance by creating community pressure on teachers. Use of WhatsApp in Indian schools has increased teacher and student attendance, student achievements as well as the quality of classroom activities. IRI programs in Ethiopia improved instruction and student skills. Television aided *Telecurso* in Brazil is an example for an alternative instruction channel delivering high quality education.

5.2. Barriers & how to overcome them

Considering successful projects, ICTs apparently have the potential to improve education in LMICs. However, as the mixed results and failure of initiatives indicate, the success of ICT-based projects is sensitive to many factors - just providing the technology is obviously not sufficient. Also, the transfer of high quality educational solutions, designed in developed countries, into the contexts of LMICs is not promising (Gulati, 2008, p. 4). So what needs to be considered to make ICTs in education successful? Reviewing the discussed insights and considering literature on key aspects, this section compiles the factors that appear to be crucial in the execution of ICT-initiatives in education in LMICs.

A frequent criticism on such projects regards the lack of a holistic approach. Educational contexts across the world are heterogeneous, depending on local circumstances. It is therefore important to consider the specific context to develop an effective initiative.

Some of the main success factors for ICT in education can be summarized as: **People**, **technology**, and **pedagogy** (Sharma et al., 2004). A major part of the insights of the above analysis can be described in this framework. In order to group remaining findings, this paper introduces two additional categories: **financial cost** and **organization**.

Concerning **people**, an initiative firstly needs to be accepted and welcomed by the affected community. Otherwise, concerns can provoke resistance. Mistrust towards or fear of the technology because of cultural beliefs might result in individuals undermining the project, parents holding children back from attending classes or teachers refusing to apply it. Another important aspect is the consideration of language and culture. Especially children in primary schools might require teaching in their local language. Likewise, including cultural components into learning contents is essential. Minorities might disapprove of the provided materials if their own history and religion are not mentioned in the curriculum. Moreover, teachers and students need to be instructed on the use of the applied technology. Lack of knowledge on handling such technologies – digital illiteracy – is widespread; introducing modern ICTs can be challenging in this context. Projects focusing on technology and neglecting digital illiteracy frequently fail (STOA, 2015, p. 14). Although ICTs can enable inclusion and decrease gaps such as based on gender or region, critics argue that ICTs widen education gaps by benefitting those who are better off more while leaving the already disadvantaged behind. For example, people who have access to the internet can enjoy free online courses, whereas remote, marginalized, poorly educated populations cannot access them due to cultural reasons, lacking power and internet supply, digital illiteracy or affordability. This gap is known as digital divide (Barrantes, 2007, p. 2; dela Pena-Bandalaria, 2007, p. 2; Gulati, 2008, pp. 2-6; ITU, 2017, p. 10-34; STOA, 2015, pp. 19-30; Tinio, 2003, p. 19). In order to close those gaps, projects that specifically aim at the disadvantaged need to be initiated, by targeting infrastructure, special trainings, and improved technology access. Community centers are one such measure that provide free or low cost access to ICTs, training on their usage, and ICT enabled education (Haddad, 2007, p. 11; STOA, 2015, pp. 29-30). The socio-economic situation in targeted communities is another crucial aspect: in poor communities, devices for educational purpose might “disappear” because of their monetary value. In such cases, strategies to ensure their security need to be implemented, for example locking the equipment in secure places.

With regards to **technology**, the possibilities supported by the local infrastructure need to be kept in mind. Does the planned project require power supply, internet- or tele-communication coverage? If yes, are these networks and related services already existent or can otherwise be arranged? A lack of internet at schools can for example be compensated by implementing a local intranet with regularly updated content which allows students to explore information (Thapa & Sein, 2018, pp. 1-7).

Since the late 1990s, the availability of electricity, network coverage, and access to as well as use of technologies in LMICs has grown, but the pace varies across and within countries and has still left out many regions. For network operators, expanding coverage to rural areas is not profitable as additional costs to ensure reliable power provision, road access, and involved buildings accrue. Currently, a majority of the population in LMICs lives in areas where power and internet supply are still not given or its usage costly, whereas mobile cellular coverage has expanded (GSMA, 2016, pp. 2-8; STOA, 2015, pp. 10-20). Figures 3, 4, and 5 indicate the recent progress in access to electricity, use of mobile cellular services, and of the internet by countries' development status.

Figure 3: Access to electricity

Figure 4: Internet users

(Source: World Bank Group, 2018, p. 165)

Figure 5: Mobile cellular subscriptions

(Source: ITU, 2017, p. 7)

Costs for mobile phone services or devices involved in education initiatives might prevent students from participating if they need to bear them (de la Pena-Bandalaria, 2007, p. 8; GSMA, 2018, p. 13-38; Gulati, 2008, pp. 5-12; STOA, 2015, p. 24). Promising efforts involving the private and public sector are being developed to improve the supply of electricity, mobile, and internet services (BRCK, 2018a, GSMA, 2016, pp. 3-26; Shapshak, 2017; Wagner, 2014, p. 66).

Apart from the infrastructure, one needs to reflect whether the planned devices are already used in the target group or need to be provided. Additionally, an ongoing technical support and maintenance for the involved ICTs must be organized. Although this factor was not discussed in the analyzed cases, Tedre et al. (2011) mention another aspect. The authors notice that environmental conditions need to be considered in the choice of the technology, as climate and temperature can for example impact the functionality of laptops. Each solution provides different prospects and limitations. Ultimately, one might prefer to consider if the educational objectives can be achieved by using technologies which are already spread in the targeted group.

With respect to **pedagogy**, adequate teacher training is a major prerequisite. Many of the discussed shortcomings in learning outcomes can be attributed to teachers' lack of knowledge about the use of the technology and pedagogical approaches of implementing them in classroom activities. When introducing technologies for education, the availability of quality content needs to be guaranteed. As mentioned in the category "people", involved contents should be aligned to the applied environment and be linked to the local curriculum in order to monitor learning progress. Lastly, the technology's usability needs to be ascertained. Pilot tests can help to assess whether the developed education program is comprehensible and motivating for students.

Financial cost is a frequently neglected aspect. It is important to not only consider initial fixed costs related to physical facilities, equipment, and production of materials, but also recurring costs including maintenance and technical support, professional development, salaries of involved personnel as well as transmission and connectivity costs such as electricity and mobile or internet coverage. For example, broadcasting as such is relatively cheap, but expenses related to administration and planning, program conceptualization and production, transmission of the courses, and their reception by the audience as well as complementary inputs such as printed materials and teacher training are substantial (McQuaide, 2009; Nettleton, 1991, pp. 110-112; Tinio, 2003). Is the planned project cost-effective and are enough funds available? Who will bear which costs?

This aspect also relates to the last category, **organization**. Organization is especially important to ensure a continuance of the education project over a long period. In an early phase, piloting and evaluating the concept help to verify its functioning. Later, ongoing project monitoring and assessments allow to detect unforeseen threats, intervene, and prevent failure. To facilitate a streamlined functioning of ICT-initiatives involving various stakeholders, policy frameworks need to be considered and systems to be aligned. Local political support, open to educational reforms, is essential to achieve a continuation of the initiative without outside support. Therefore, it is often stressed that for larger education programs, the government's support is crucial (Tedre, 2011; Thapa & Sein, S. 1-7, 2018). External initiators such as NGOs can only act as catalysts and their support is likely to end. Due to the dependence of their funds on scheduled goals, local actors should be involved to take over responsibility at a defined time and secure the continu-

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ance of all necessary support. To ensure longevity, responsibilities for ownership, financing, and preservation of technology as well as pedagogical approaches need to be clearly assigned. Such responsibilities are handled in different ways. Sometimes related tasks are assigned to a department within the ministry of education, a telecom regulator or ministries of communication or ICT. Others integrate those responsibilities across the education system. For several reasons, establishing a new organization dedicated solely to ICT in education can be useful, whereas established institutions are often conservative, resisting new approaches. Furthermore, ICTs in education require technical and business skills that are usually not prevalent in existing institutions. As a variety of business and government stakeholders need to be coordinated, independence from these actors is helpful (Trucano, 2014, pp. 109-112). Setting up a dedicated organization to handle national ICT initiatives in education might be decisive for their long term success.

6. Conclusion

The purpose of this paper was to analyze the dispersed knowledge on different aspects of the use of ICTs in education in LMICs and to evaluate in how far they can compensate for deficiencies in education. Insights from the literature – including case studies and research articles related to education and ICTs – were analyzed and suggestions elaborated on how to effectively apply ICTs in education to contribute to the education targets declared in the SDG 4.

ICT, education, and its combination constitute a complex matter that involves numerous aspects. This paper undertook efforts to provide an overview of the most important aspects. However, due to its limited scope it was not feasible to address every involved facet. It is therefore possible that some relevant topics have not been discussed and the author does not make any claim for a completeness of content. Nonetheless, this paper shall serve as a helpful reference point for relevant stakeholders to prevent the design of inappropriate initiatives and act as a guideline for involved actors.

Studies on different ICTs have shown that they can contribute to the international education targets: **Access, inclusion, and gender equality** as well as **quality**. However, many initiatives fail to take a holistic view by neglecting the local context of the targeted pop-

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ulation. As has been elaborated in the analysis, the author argues that **people, technology, pedagogy, financial cost, and organization** are the key aspects that need to be considered in the planning of an ICT initiative in education in LMICs.

Comparing modern to “old” technologies (radio, television, and mobile phones), the analysis indicates that refocusing on older technologies might be more promising than on recent, in the education sector hyped ICTs. Programs relying on traditional technologies can result in remarkable educational success, and difficulties based on deficient infrastructure, additional costs, and digital illiteracy can be avoided.

In general, many shortcomings in the education sector persist which ICTs can compensate. As the affected LMICs frequently do not possess the necessary resources, the international community will need to increase support for education efforts to achieve the SDG 4 targets by 2030. Apart from financial aid, an especially promising area for international aid is the support in policy and regulatory frameworks and in providing related infrastructures. These measures would reduce systemic constraints that are common in LMICs and contribute to improving the accessibility to ICT enabled services as well as their affordability through resulting price decreases.

While there is no specific, universal best-practice instruction on which ICT or ICT-combination to use in a certain way to guarantee a success in improving education, the make-or-break factors that should be considered in the planning of such projects are summarized in figure 6. Figure 7 shows in more detail concrete pitfalls that can frequently be encountered. Governments, NGOs, donors, policy makers, and other stakeholders might use this overview as a checklist in the planning of ICT-aided education initiatives or to determine focus areas for their support. Together, figure 6 and 7 constitute a practical guide that will allow them to learn from past mistakes to avoid failure of future undertakings and help to reap the full potential of ICTs to improve education in LMICs.

Figure 6: Make-or-break factors in education related ICT initiatives

(Own figure)

Figure 7: Checklist for education related ICT initiatives

Barriers & Prerequisites	Critical domain	Potential remedies
1 Mistrust towards technology/ initiative	People	Promote & explain benefits
2 Disapproval/ inappropriateness of provided content	People	Include local culture (history & religion), consider language requirements
3 Digital illiteracy	People	Training (teachers, students, community) on usage of the technology
4 Theft of provided devices	People	Provide lockers
5 Lack of reliable electricity/ telecommunication/internet coverage	Technology	Alternative solutions: Solar power, local networks, intranet
6 Planned project requires devices & network services that are not given in the target group	Technology	Verify penetration of involved devices & services in the community and introduce them if necessary
7 Gradual dysfunction of involved technology	Technology	Ongoing technical support and maintenance for the involved ICTs
8 Extreme environmental conditions	Technology	Special requirements on technology: Heat/ water/ dust resistance
9 Teachers don't know how to integrate the technology in instruction	Pedagogy	Train teachers, provide affective pedagogical approaches
10 Teachers uncertain about students' progression	Pedagogy	Link the program to the curriculum & include assessments
11 Deficient usability of the program: Children cannot handle tasks	Pedagogy	Detect deficiencies by conducting pilot tests and monitoring
12 No long-term responsibility for costs allocated	Cost	Strategy of covering 1) initial fixed & 2) recurring costs 1) Physical facilities, equipment & production of materials 2) Maintenance & technical support, professional development, salaries, transmission & connectivity costs
13 Costs too high, not efficient	Cost	Determine relative cost efficiency
14 Reliance on external organization (their withdrawal ends the program)	Organization	Allocate responsibilities: Ownership, financing & preservation of technology, pedagogical approaches
15 Coordination of involved stakeholders deficient	Organization	Ensure streamlined functioning, aligned systems, appropriate policy frameworks & political support

(Own figure)

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